

**COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF SOMATIC PHRASEOLOGY
EXPRESSING JOY, CALMNESS, SURPRISE AND COURAGE (ON THE
EXAMPLE OF GERMAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES)**

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Abstract: *In this article, somatic phraseology expressing joy, calmness, surprise and courage in German and Uzbek languages is cross-analyzed, examples are given, and alternative variants of phraseology in both languages are identified.*

Key words: *phraseology, somatic phraseology, concept, connotative meaning, cross-sectional analysis.*

Joy is one of the next positive emotions included in our materials. In the SFs expressing joy in German, such words as Herz (heart), Kopf (head), Hand (hand), Backen (temple), Gesicht (face), Ohr (ear) participated as base words. The following phrases include: *das Herz springt jmdm. vor Freude* “sevinchdan yuragi hapqirdi”; *die Bude auf den Kopf stellen* “xursandchilik qilmoq”; *Herzklopfen haben/ bekommen* “(sevinchdan) yuragi qinidan chiqmoq”; *jmdm. lacht/ hüpt das Herz im Leibe* “ko‘ngli ko‘tarilmoq”; *sich die Hände reiben* “og‘zi qulog‘ida bo‘lmoq”; *über beide/alle vier Backen grinsen/ strahlen* “yuzi kulmoq, chehrasi ochilmoq”; *über das ganze Gesicht lachen (strahlen)* “yuzi kulmoq”; *von einem Ohr [bis] zum anderen lachen/ strahlen* “og‘zi qulog‘ida bo‘lmoq”.

The image of a person who is extremely happy, happy and experiencing joy is reflected in the Uzbek language in the image of a person whose whole body and movements are relaxed, and because of this, he does not walk on the ground, but flies and even reaches the sky with his head (*boshi ko‘kda (osmonda), boshi*

ko'kka (osmonga) yetdi, boshini ko'kka (osmonga) yetkazmoq). Also, the names of body parts such as heart (*bahri dili ochildi, bahri dilini ochmoq, dili yoridi, dili ochildi, qulfi dili ochildi*), chest (*ko'kragi tog'day ko'tarildi, ko'ksi ko'tarildi*), heart (*ko'ngil yorishdi, ko'ngil ochmoq, ko'ngilni yorishtirmoq, ko'ngli yozildi, ko'ngli tog'day ko'tarildi, ko'nglini ko'tarmoq*), mouth (*og'zi qulog'iga yetdi, og'zi qulog'ida*), foot, hand (*oyog'i olti, qo'li yetti*), heart (*sevinchi yuragiga sig'maydi, sevinchini yuragiga sig'dirolmaslik, yuragi qoq yorila yozdi*), skin (*terisiga sig'may ketdi, terisiga sig'may*).

Somatic phraseology in German describes the feeling of surprise, which expresses a short-term emotional reaction to unexpected external factors, expresses the image of a person who is surprised and surprised: (*fast*) *auf den Rücken fallen* “yoqasini ushlamoq”, (*grosse*) *Augen machen* “ko'zi chanog'idan chiqib keta yozdi”, *den Mund/ das Maul aufsperrern* “og'zi ochilib qoldi”, *die Augen aufreißen* “aqli shoshdi”, *ein Gesicht machen, als hätten einem die Hühner das Brot weggefressen* “hayratga tushmoq”, *Mund und Nase aufreißen/ aufsperrern* “og'zi ochilib qoldi”, *seinen [eigenen] Augen nicht trauen wollen* “ko'zlariga ishonmaslik”, *seinen Ohren (Augen) nicht treuen* “quloqlariga ishonmaslik”, *sich an den Kopf schlagen (wollen)* “hang-mang bo'lib qolmoq”, *sich nicht von der Hand weisen lassen (yoki nicht von der Hand zu weisen sein)* “aql bovar qilmaslik, aqliga sig'dirolmaslik”.

In the Uzbek language, the image of a surprised person is defined by the fact that the eyes are enlarged to the extent that they come out of their sockets (*ko'zi chanog'idan chiqib keta yozdi*), the mouth is wide open or remains open (*og'zi ochildi, og'zi ochilib qoldi, og'zini ochirmoq, og'zini ochmoq*). As in German, in Uzbek the feeling of surprise is interpreted as disbelief. The Uzbek phrase *ko'ziga ishonmaslik* has the meaning of doubting that what one sees or what is happening in reality exists and is so, to be very surprised.

In Uzbek, SF means a feeling of discomfort: *Es herrscht Heulen und*

Zähneknirschen/ Zähneklappern “vahimaga tushmoq”, *jmdm. schlägt das Herz bis zum Hals* “yuragi taka-puka bo‘lmoq”, *jmds. Herz schlägt höher* “yuragi hapqirdi” FBlari nemis tilida, *ko‘ngilning bir chekkasi g‘ash, ko‘ngilning bir chekkasi xira, ko‘ngliga g‘ulg‘ula solmoq, ko‘ngliga g‘ulg‘ula tushdi, yuragiga g‘ulg‘ula solmoq, yuragiga g‘ulg‘ula tushdi, yuragini taka-puka qilib yubormoq.*

On the contrary, the state of a calm person is reflected in the German language by phraseologisms involving the somatic lexical units Seele (soul), Kopf (head), Herz (heart), Blut (blood), Haare (hair): (*dann/ jetzt hat die arme/ liebe Seele Ruh* “ko‘ngli taskin topdi”, *einen kühlen/ klaren Kopf bewahren* “bosiqlik bilan ish ko‘rmoq”, *jmdm. eine Last von der Seele nehmen* “ko‘ngli joyiga tushmoq”, *jmdm. geht das Herz auf* “ko‘ngli joyiga tushmoq”, *kalttes Blut bewahren* “o‘zini bosmoq”, *ruhig[es] Blut bewahren* “xotirjam bo‘lmoq”, *sich wegen/ über etw. keine grauen Haare wachsen lassen* “e‘tibor qilmaslik, o‘zini xotirjam tutmoq”).

In the Uzbek SFs belonging to this semantic group, the lexeme *ko‘ngil* (*ko‘ngil to‘q, ko‘ngilni to‘q qilmoq, ko‘ngli joyiga tushdi, ko‘nglini joyiga tushirmoq, ko‘nglini to‘q tutmoq*) is used in Uzbek language. It was observed that he participated. Also, in the Uzbek language, the phraseology *nisbatan oyoq uzatmoq, suyagi tinch, suyagi tinchib qoldi* for a person who is relieved of all his worries, is calm, and for a calm person who can control his actions, the phraseology *o‘zini qo‘lga olmoq* is used.

One of the integral parts of a person's inner world is his traits and character traits. Among the collected and analyzed materials, the large number of SFs belonging to this group requires their classification and study into subgroups: 1) positive characteristics; 2) negative human characteristics.

The names of the body parts of the eye (Auge), heart (Herz) and shoulder, neck (Nacken) are involved in German SFs expressing courage. In the phrase *Dem Tod in die Augen schauen* (*dem Tod ins Auge sehen*) "to look death in the

eye", bravery is represented by " o‘limning ko‘ziga tik boqish".

REFERENCES:

1. Faro K. Somatismen als Problem der dännischen und deutschen Lexikographie. In: Morgensen J. E., Gottlieb H., Zettersten A. Symposium on Lexicography Maz 4-6. 2000 at the University of Copenhagen. – Tübingen: Niemeyer, 2002. –S. 107-124.
2. Imyaminova Sh.S. Nemis tili frazeologiyasi. O‘quv qo‘llanma –Toshkent: Mumtoz so‘z, 2011. -93 b.
3. Klimaszewska Z. Die Phraseologie auf kulturhistorischem Hintergrund am Beispiel des Deutschen, Niederländischen und Polnischen. In: Iwasaki, Eijiro: Begegnung mit dem Fremden. Grenzen-Traditionen-Vergleiche. Akten des VIII. Internationalen Germanisten-Kongresses. Bd.4. –München: Iudicium Verlag, 1991. –S. 362-369.
4. Latipov O. J. Rus, o‘zbek, ingliz va nemis tillarida “bosh” komponenti bilan hosil bo‘lgan iboralar xususida. O‘zbekistonda xorijiy tillar” ilmiy–metodik elektron jurnal. №3 (22)/2018. –B. 58-63.
5. Latipov O. J. Rus, o‘zbek, ingliz va nemis tillarida “qo‘l” komponenti bilan bog‘liq iboralar. O‘zbekistonda xorijiy tillar” ilmiy-metodik elektron jurnal. №2/2019. –B. 70–76.
6. Lundh K. Äquivalente Somatismen der deutschen und Schwedischen - wie soll das kontrastive Modell aussehen? –Frankfurt (Main): De Gruyter, 1994. –S. 163-173.
7. Pinel Lopez R. M. Ein Vergleich sprachlich modifizierter Phraseologismen in deutschen und spanischen Werbeanzeigen. In: Wotjak G. Studien zum romanisch–deutschen und innerromanischen Sprachvergleich. Akten der III. Internationalen Arbeitstagung zum romanisch–deutschen

- Sprachvergleich. –Frankfurt am Main/Berlin/ Bern: De Gruyter, 1997. –S. 213-223.
8. Sadikov Z.Ya. Yusuf Xos Hojib “Qutadg‘u bilig” asarining nemischa va inglizcha tarjimalari qiyosiy tahlili. Filologiya fanlari doktori (DSc) dissertatsiyasi avtoreferati. – Toshkent, 2020. –65 b.
9. Umarjonova G.M. Nemis va o‘zbek tillaridagi “Hand” “qo‘l” komponentli frazeologizmlarning chog‘ishtirma tahlili. Filologiya fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori dissertatsiyasi avtoreferati. –Farg‘ona, 2022. –53 b.
- 10.Umarxo‘jayev M.I., Nazarov K.N. Nemischa-ruscha-o‘zbekcha frazeologik lug‘at. –Toshkent: O‘qituvchi, 1994. –160 b.
- 11.Weng J. Der Mensch und sein Körper in deutschen und chinesischesen Phraseologismen. In: Iwasaki, Eijiro: Begegnung mit dem Fremden. Grenzen-Traditionen-Vergleiche. Akten des VIII. Internationalen Germanisten-Kongresses. Bd.4. –München/ Tokio: W. De Gruyter, 1991. – S. 380-388.
- 12.Вакк Ф.О. О соматической фразеологии в современном эстонском литературном языке: Автореф. дисс. канд. филол. наук. –Таллин, 1964. –22 с.